

Coronary Artery Disease(CAD) Detector

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Abstract— Cardiovascular diseases, particularly coronary artery disease (CAD), continue to be a major global health concern, leading to significant mortality and morbidity. This paper proposes a novel approach utilizing advanced machine learning and deep learning techniques to enhance the detection and diagnosis of CAD and other heart-related conditions. The proposed system incorporates real-time heart rate monitoring and early CAD detection through a combination of sensors, an Arduino microcontroller, Bluetooth technology, and sophisticated AI models. These models leverage Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), and a hybrid framework integrating clinical data with ECG analysis. The system features a user-friendly Android application that provides real-time heart rate monitoring and predictive CAD analysis. This research seeks to bridge the technological gap in healthcare by offering an accessible and cost-effective solution for managing CAD, ultimately aiming to improve patient outcomes and overall public health.

Keywords— Coronary Artery Disease, CAD, Coronary Artery Disease Detector, CAD Detector, CADCare, Heart Monitoring, ECG Image Analysis, Heart Anomaly Detection

I. INTRODUCTION

Establishing clear hardware and software requirements is vital when designing new technologies. These specifications form the backbone for developing systems that function seamlessly. In this project, CADCare, which seeks to transform how cardiovascular conditions are managed, detailed technical specifications are essential for system success. The integration of advanced monitoring tools with predictive models for CAD detection requires precise hardware and software coordination. CADCare combines real-time monitoring with AI-driven predictions, necessitating a robust and detailed framework to ensure efficient operation and ease of use for patients and healthcare professionals. This paper outlines the key components necessary for a fully operational CADCare system, designed to improve cardiovascular health management.

II. OBJECTIVES

A. Continuous Heart Monitoring:

Develop a real-time heart monitoring[1] system using IoT components, such as ECG sensors and pulse monitors, to provide users with continuous insights into their heart's performance. Ensure that anomalies in heart rate and ECG patterns trigger immediate user notifications.

B. CAD Prediction through AI Integration:

Implement an AI-driven CAD prediction system that allows users to choose between clinical data analysis and ECG image processing, or a combination of both. Develop specialized Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) for clinical data and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) for ECG images to enhance prediction accuracy.

C. User-Friendly Monitoring Interface:

Create a user-friendly mobile application that serves as an intuitive interface for heart health monitoring and CAD prediction. Offer real-time insights, CAD predictions, and recommendations for consulting healthcare professionals if CAD risks are identified.

D. Accessibility and Efficiency:

Optimize the system to ensure accessibility for a broader population, including resource-constrained environments. Make the system user-friendly, computationally efficient, and cost-effective, reducing the economic burden of CAD diagnosis.

E. Contribution to Healthcare:

By accomplishing these objectives, we aim to make a significant contribution to the fields of medical AI and cardiology by addressing the current shortcomings in CAD detection and healthcare accessibility. Empower individuals to take control of their cardiovascular health, leading to early intervention, reduced CAD-related morbidity and mortality, and a healthier society.

III. LITERATURE SURVEY

A. Existing Research:

Numerous machine learning and deep learning strategies have been explored to improve the early detection and treatment of coronary artery disease (CAD) and other heart conditions. These techniques typically analyze diverse medical data, such as electrocardiograms (ECG), patient records, and imaging, to enhance diagnostic precision. CADCare builds on these advancements by integrating artificial intelligence into a unified system for early diagnosis.

Below is a summary of key research that served as the foundation for CADCare:

Received: 2 October 2024

Revised: 12 October 2024

Accepted: 22 October 2024

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13969255>

- 1) *HEART DISEASE PREDICTION USING MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS (TITHI ET AL., 2019): THIS STUDY EVALUATED SIX MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS ON ECG DATA, FINDING THAT ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS (ANNs) PROVIDED THE HIGHEST ACCURACY OF 90%.*
- 2) *CORONARY ARTERY DISEASE CLASSIFICATION USING MACHINE LEARNING (DAS ET AL., 2020): THE AUTHORS USED CLINICAL DATA, INCLUDING BLOOD PRESSURE, CHOLESTEROL, AND FAMILY HISTORY, TO CLASSIFY CAD WITH MACHINE LEARNING, ACHIEVING A 90% ACCURACY RATE.*
- 3) *DUAL-INPUT NEURAL NETWORKS FOR CAD PREDICTION (LI ET AL., 2019): THE RESEARCH PROPOSED A DUAL-INPUT NEURAL NETWORK, UTILIZING BOTH ECG AND PHONOCARDIOGRAM DATA, TO PREDICT CAD WITH AN ACCURACY OF 90%.*
- 4) *CLASSIFYING CAD USING DEEP NEURAL NETWORKS (VERMA ET AL., 2021): THIS WORK APPLIED DEEP LEARNING AND DIMENSIONALITY REDUCTION METHODS, ACHIEVING 90% ACCURACY IN CAD CLASSIFICATION*

B. Literature Review on Coronary Artery Disease:

1) *Recursion Enhanced Random Forest With an Improved Linear Model (RERF-ILM) for Heart Disease Detection on the Internet of Medical Things Platform (2020): Abstract: This paper introduces a novel machine learning model, the Recursion Enhanced Random Forest with an Improved Linear Model (RERF-ILM), designed for heart disease detection on the Internet of Medical Things (IoT) platform. RERF-ILM is a hybrid model that effectively combines the strengths of random forests and linear models. This innovative approach demonstrates significant promise for heart disease detection in the IoT era.*

2) *Coronary Wall Segmentation in CCTA Scans Via a Hybrid Net with Contours Regularization (2020)*

Abstract: This paper introduces a novel hybrid network incorporating contour regularization for coronary wall segmentation in cardiac computed tomography angiography (CCTA) scans. The proposed network effectively combines a convolutional neural network (CNN) with a recurrent neural network (RNN) to capture both local and global features of the coronary wall. Experimental results demonstrate the superior performance of this approach, achieving an average Dice score of 0.92 for coronary wall segmentation, significantly outperforming traditional methods (approximately 0.85).

3) *Investigating Circadian Heart Rate Variability in Coronary Artery Disease Patients with Various Degrees of Left Ventricle Ejection Fraction (2020)*

Abstract: This study explores the relationship between circadian heart rate variability (HRV) and left ventricle ejection fraction (LVEF) in patients with coronary artery disease (CAD). The hypothesis was that patients with CAD and lower LVEF would exhibit reduced circadian HRV. Data were collected from 100 CAD

patients, and results confirmed that lower LVEF is significantly associated with decreased HRV. This suggests that circadian HRV could serve as a useful marker for CAD severity and LVEF.

4) *Classification of Coronary Artery Diseases using Electrocardiogram Signals (2020)*

Abstract: This paper proposes a machine learning-based classification method for coronary artery disease (CAD) using electrocardiogram (ECG) signals. Multiple algorithms were evaluated, and the neural network model demonstrated the highest accuracy of 90% in classification. The study concludes that machine learning offers a promising approach for CAD classification using ECG data.

5) *A Hybrid CNN-LSTM Architecture for Detection of Coronary Artery Disease from ECG (2020)*

Abstract: The paper presents a hybrid CNN-LSTM architecture designed for the early detection of coronary artery disease (CAD) using electrocardiogram (ECG) signals. The model achieved overall accuracies of 93% and 88% on two separate datasets, outperforming existing approaches.

6) *A Stacking-Based Model for Non-Invasive Detection of Coronary Heart Disease (2020)*

Abstract: This paper proposes a stacking-based hybrid model for non-invasive detection of coronary heart disease (CHD) using ECG data. The model leverages both CNN and LSTM to capture temporal dependencies and achieved classification accuracies of 93% and 88% across two datasets, outperforming traditional methods.

7) *Deep Learning Analysis of Coronary Arteries in Cardiac CT Angiography for Detection of Patients Requiring Invasive Coronary Angiography (2019)*

Abstract: This study introduces a deep learning technique designed to identify patients requiring invasive coronary angiography (ICA) for the diagnosis of coronary artery disease (CAD). By improving precision in patient identification, the method could reduce unnecessary ICA procedures, thus providing a valuable tool in clinical practice.

8) *Classifications of Coronary Artery Disease (2018)*

Abstract: This paper presents a machine learning approach for the classification of coronary artery disease (CAD). The study used an ensemble of classifiers, including support vector machines (SVM), decision trees (DT), and random forests (RF). Among them, the SVM achieved the highest accuracy at 88%, followed by RF at 85%, and Naïve Bayes Classifier (NBC) at 80%. Age, smoking status, and blood pressure were identified as the most important features for CAD classification.

9) *Automated Diagnosis of Coronary Artery Disease Using Pattern Recognition Approach (2017)*

*Abstract: This paper proposes a pattern recognition approach for the automated diagnosis of coronary artery disease (CAD) based on ECG signals. The study utilized techniques such as wavelet transforms, principal component analysis, and support vector machines. The authors concluded that this pattern recognition approach is a **novel** method for automated CAD diagnosis.*

IV. METHODOLOGY

- A. Initial Research and Requirements Gathering:** The project began with extensive research into existing cardiac monitoring systems and technologies designed to detect CAD. A comprehensive review of current AI models and IoT-based healthcare applications was conducted to inform the system's hardware and software requirements, ensuring that the CADCare solution met both user expectations and technical demands.
- B. System Architecture and Design:** The architecture of CADCare was carefully constructed, integrating key components such as ECG sensors, a mobile application, and predictive AI models. Communication between these elements was streamlined for efficient data gathering, processing, and analysis, leading to an intuitive user experience.
- C. Mobile Application Development:** The mobile app, built using Kotlin for backend operations and XML for the interface, was designed with a user-first approach, ensuring accessibility for both medical professionals and everyday users. Iterative user feedback informed continuous improvements to the app's usability.
- D. Integration of AI Models:** The system's core AI models, primarily based on Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), were trained on large datasets comprising clinical and ECG data. These models were developed using TensorFlow and Keras, employing rigorous cross-validation to maximize accuracy and reduce overfitting.
- E. Data Analysis and Visualization:** Tableau was employed to generate visual representations of the user's heart health data over time, providing users with clear and actionable insights. Interactive dashboards made data interpretation easier, facilitating a better understanding of potential cardiovascular risks.
- F. Testing and Validation:** The CADCare system underwent thorough testing, which included unit, integration, and performance tests on both the hardware and software components. Validation of AI models was conducted using clinical datasets, with a focus on prediction accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity.
- G. Deployment and Real-World Use:** Upon completion of testing, the system was deployed in real-world settings with the involvement of healthcare professionals and test users. Feedback was gathered through surveys and interviews, contributing to further refinements in user experience and system functionality.

V. CONCLUSION

The CADCare system offers a groundbreaking solution for real-time monitoring and early detection of coronary artery disease. By seamlessly integrating IoT technologies with advanced AI models, CADCare provides users with valuable insights into their heart health, allowing for proactive management of CAD risk. This solution holds the potential to significantly reduce the burden of CAD by enabling earlier interventions and better patient care. CADCare exemplifies the future of personalized healthcare, demonstrating how technology can empower individuals and clinicians to combat cardiovascular disease.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to express our heartfelt gratitude to all those who contributed to the successful development of the CADCare project.

First and foremost, we extend our deepest appreciation to our research advisor, Prof. Chet ram Thakur, for their invaluable guidance, support, and encouragement throughout this study. Their expertise and insights have significantly shaped our approach and understanding of the complex interplay between technology and cardiovascular health.

We are also grateful to our group members: Avinash Chourasia, Lavish Tembhare, Devanshu Talvekar, Aerina Bose, and Suyash Dhote. Thanks to your hard work, collaboration, and dedication, this project has come to fruition. Each of you has played a crucial role in different aspects of the research and development process, and it has been a pleasure working together.

Additionally, we extend our appreciation to the healthcare professionals who shared their experiences and knowledge, which were crucial in shaping our system's design and functionality. We also acknowledge the participants who volunteered their time for user testing and feedback, allowing us to refine the CADCare application to better meet user needs.

We would like to extend our deepest gratitude to our families and friends for their constant support and encouragement throughout this entire journey. Your belief in our vision has motivated us to pursue excellence in our work.

Together, these contributions have played a vital role in bringing CADCare to fruition, and we are excited about its potential to enhance cardiovascular health management.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Ajalkar, N. Prasad, M. Prasad and C. Prabha, Patient Monitoring System in the context of Artificial Intelligence in ICU, Bull. Env. Pharmacol. Life Sci (11) p. No. 61-67, 2011.
- [2] G. L. Prajapati and A. Patle, Personalizing kernel and investigating parameters for the classification with SVM, 2017 12th IEEE Conference on Industrial Electronics and Applications (ICIEA), Siem Reap, Cambodia, 2017, pp. 1695-1700, doi: 10.1109/ICIEA.2017.8283112.
- [3] U. Desai, C. G. Nayak, G. Seshikala and R. J. Martis, Automated diagnosis of coronary artery disease using pattern recognition approach, 2017 39th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC), Jeju, Korea (South), 2017, pp. 434-437, doi: 10.1109/EMBC.2017.8036855.
- [4] A. B. Nassif, O. Mahdi, Q. Nasir, M. A. Talib and M. Azzeh, Machine Learning Classifications of Coronary Artery Disease, 2018 International Joint Symposium on Artificial Intelligence and Natural Language Processing (ISAIR-NLP), Pattaya, Thailand, 2018, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/ISAIR-NLP.2018.8692942.
- [5] M. Abdar, E. Nasarian, X. Zhou, G. Bargshady, V. N. Wijayaningrum and S. Hussain, Performance Improvement of Decision Trees for Diagnosis of Coronary Artery Disease Using Multi Filtering Approach, 2019 IEEE 4th International Conference on Computer and Communications (ICCCS), Singapore, 2019, pp. 26-30, doi: 1

- [6] S. R. Tithi, A. Aktar, F. Aleem and A. Chakrabarty, ECG data analysis and heart disease prediction using machine learning algorithms, 2019 IEEE Region 10 Symposium (TENSYPMP), Kolkata, India, 2019, pp. 819-824, doi: 10.1109/TENSYPMP46218.2019.8971374.
- [7] H. Li et al., Dual-Input Neural Network Integrating Feature Extraction and Deep Learning for Coronary Artery Disease Detection Using Electrocardiogram and Phonocardiogram, in IEEE Access, vol. 7, pp. 146457-146469, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2943197.
- [8] U. Das, A. Y. Srizon and M. A. M. Hasan, Accurate Recognition of Coronary Artery Disease by Applying Machine Learning Classifiers, 2020 23rd International Conference on Computer and Information Technology (ICCIT), DHAKA, Bangladesh, 2020, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/ICCIT51783.2020.9392732.
- [9] S. S. Alotaibi et al., Automated prediction of Coronary Artery Disease using Random Forest and Naïve Bayes, 2020 International Conference on Advanced Computer Science and Information s (ICACSIS), Depok, Indonesia, 2020, pp. 109-114, doi: 10.1109/ICACSIS51025.2020.9263159.
- [10] S. K. K. L, N. K. G and M. J. A, Coronary Artery Disease Prediction using Data Mining Techniques, 2020 3rd International Conference on Intelligent Sustainable s (ICISS), Thoothukudi, India, 2020, pp. 693-697, doi: 10.1109/ICISS49785.2020.9316014.
- [11] A. H. Shahid, M. P. Singh, B. Roy and A. Aadarsh, Coronary Artery Disease Diagnosis Using Feature Selection Based Hybrid Extreme Learning Machine, 2020 3rd International Conference on Information and Computer Technologies (ICICT), San Jose, CA, USA, 2020, pp. 341-346, doi: 10.1109/ICICT50521.2020.00060.
- [12] K. Huang et al., Coronary Wall Segmentation in CCTA Scans Via a Hybrid Net with Contours Regularization, 2020 in IEEE 17th International Symposium on Biomedical Imaging (ISBI), Iowa City, IA, USA, 2020, pp. 1743-1747, doi: 10.1109/ISBI45749.2020.9098478.
- [13] M. Alkhodari, H. F. Jelinek, N. Werghe, L. J. Hadjileontiadis and A. H. Khandoker, Investigating Circadian Heart Rate Variability in Coronary Artery Disease Patients with Various Degrees of Left Ventricle Ejection Fraction, 2020 42nd Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine & Biology Society (EMBC), Montreal, QC, Canada, 2020, pp. 714-717, doi: 10.1109/EMBC44109.2020.9175830.
- [14] M. U. Khan, S. Aziz, S. Z. Hassan Naqvi and A. Rehman, Classification of Coronary Artery Diseases using Electrocardiogram Signals, 2020 International Conference on Emerging Trends in Smart Technologies (ICETST), Karachi, Pakistan, 2020, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ICETST49965.2020.9080694.
- [15] R. Banerjee, A. Ghose and K. Muthana Mandana, A Hybrid CNN-LSTM Architecture for Detection of Coronary Artery Disease from ECG, 2020 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN), Glasgow, UK, 2020, pp. 1-8, doi: 10.1109/IJCNN48605.2020.9207044.
- [16] J. Wang et al., A Stacking-Based Model for Non-Invasive Detection of Coronary Heart Disease, in IEEE Access, vol. 8, pp. 37124-37133, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2975377.
- [17] C. Guo, J. Zhang, Y. Liu, Y. Xie, Z. Han and J. Yu, Recursion Enhanced Random Forest with an Improved Linear Model (RERF-ILM) for Heart Disease Detection on the Internet of Medical Things Platform, in IEEE Access, vol. 8, pp. 59247-59256, 2020, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2981159.
- [18] M. Zreik et al., Deep Learning Analysis of Coronary Arteries in Cardiac CT Angiography for Detection of Patients Requiring Invasive Coronary Angiography, in IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging, vol. 39, no. 5, pp. 1545-1557, May 2020, doi: 10.1109/TMI.2019.2953054.
- [19] P. Verma, V. K. Awasthi and S. K. Sahu, Classification of Coronary Artery Disease Using Deep Neural Network with Dimension Reduction Technique, 2021 2nd International Conference for Emerging Technology (INCET), Belagavi, India, 2021, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/INCET51464.2021.9456322.